

YOSH MILLIY KURASHCHILARNING MASHG‘ULOTLARINI DASTLABKI BOSQICHLARDA TA’LIM VA TARBIYA JARAYONINI INDIVIDUALLASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada yosh milliy kurashchilarning mashg‘ulotlarini dastlabki bosqichlarda tashkil etishda ta’lim va tarbiya jarayonini individuallashtirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish masalalari yoritilgan. Tadqiqot davomida sportchilarning yoshi, jismoniy tayyorgarligi, psixologik holati va individual qobiliyatlarini hisobga olgan holda mashg‘ulotlarni tashkil etishning samarali usullari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, murabbiy-pedagog faoliyatida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar, differensial yondashuv va individual rejalashtirish asosida sportchilarni tayyorlashning ahamiyati ochib berilgan. Natijada yosh kurashchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishi, texnik-taktik mahorati hamda ma’naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasini oshirishga xizmat qiluvchi metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: yosh kurashchilar, milliy kurash, individuallashtirish, ta’lim jarayoni, tarbiya jarayoni, mashg‘ulot tizimi, pedagogik texnologiyalar, differensial yondashuv, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, texnik-taktik tayyorgarlik, sport pedagogikasi, murabbiy faoliyati.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ИНДИВИДУАЛИЗАЦИИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО И ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА ЮНЫХ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ БОРЦОВ НА НАЧАЛЬНЫХ ЭТАПАХ ПОДГОТОВКИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы совершенствования механизмов индивидуализации образовательного и воспитательного процесса юных национальных борцов на начальных этапах подготовки. В ходе исследования проанализированы эффективные методы организации тренировочных занятий с учётом возраста спортсменов, уровня физической подготовленности, психологического состояния и индивидуальных способностей. Также раскрыта значимость современных педагогических технологий, дифференцированного подхода и индивидуального планирования в деятельности тренера-педагога. В результате разработаны методические рекомендации, направленные на повышение физического развития, технико-тактического мастерства и духовно-нравственного воспитания юных борцов.

Ключевые слова: юные борцы, национальная борьба, индивидуализация, образовательный процесс, воспитательный процесс, тренировочная система, педагогические технологии, дифференцированный подход, физическая подготовка, технико-тактическая подготовка, спортивная педагогика, деятельность тренера.

IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF INDIVIDUALIZING THE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROCESS OF YOUNG NATIONAL WRESTLERS AT THE INITIAL STAGES OF TRAINING

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Abstract: This article discusses the improvement of mechanisms for individualizing the educational and training process of young national wrestlers at the initial stages of training. The study analyses effective methods of organizing training sessions by considering athletes' age, physical fitness, psychological condition, and individual abilities. In addition, the importance of modern pedagogical technologies, differentiated approaches, and individual planning in the coach's pedagogical activity is highlighted. As a result, methodological recommendations aimed at improving the physical development, technical-tactical skills, and moral education of young wrestlers have been developed.

Keywords: young wrestlers, national wrestling, individualization, educational process, training process, training system, pedagogical technologies, differentiated approach, physical fitness, technical-tactical training, sports pedagogy, coaching activity.

INTRODUCTION

Research Objective. To develop proposals and recommendations for improving the mechanisms of technical training by taking into account the individual characteristics of young wrestlers.

Research Tasks: to expand the functional recovery capabilities of young wrestlers through continuous monitoring of their physical condition using the "Polar H10" heart rate (HR) monitor; to improve the coordination development of hand, leg, and waist movements in 11–12-year-old wrestlers, enhance their individual constructive combinations, and increase the effectiveness of evaluating episodic situations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Methodology. The research methodology is based on sports psychology, modern pedagogy, learner-centered education principles, and concepts aimed at developing athletes' psychological preparedness.

In addition, the following scientific approaches were used as the foundation of the study:

— Competency-based approach — formation of psychological stability, self-management, and readiness for competitive activity in athletes;

— Activity-oriented approach — integration of psychological preparation with practical activities during training and competition processes;

— Systematic approach — comprehensive development and assessment of athletes' psychological state based on cognitive, emotional, and volitional components.

Research Object. The object of the research consists of the theoretical and methodological foundations of mechanisms for individualizing the technical training of 11–12-year-old wrestlers in beginner training groups of sports schools.

Research Subject. The subject of the research is the organization of the training process aimed at increasing the effectiveness of mastering technical techniques by considering the individual characteristics of 11–12-year-old wrestlers.

Research Methods. The following research methods were used in the study: analysis and review of scientific-methodological literature, questionnaires, pedagogical observations, analysis of the training process, pedagogical experiment, pedagogical testing, anthropometry, pulsometry, dynamometry, use of Polar H10 equipment, and mathematical-statistical methods.

Scientific Novelty of the Research. The scientific novelty of the research lies in the continuous monitoring of young wrestlers' physical condition using the "Polar H10" heart rate (HR) monitor, as well as the individual integration of cognitive reaction speed, situational analysis

skills, psychomotor response dynamics, and opponent-reading strategies through an online profiling system. This approach minimized excessive oxygen consumption and injury risks while expanding the athletes' individual cardiorespiratory functional recovery capabilities.

In wrestling, technical techniques are performed in accordance with a methodological execution sequence, while the method of establishing contact with the opponent, the initiation of movement, the execution phase of the throw, and the final positions are strictly controlled. In this process, along with movement speed, accuracy, balance, rhythm maintenance, and the ability to coordinate movements against external forces when necessary are also evaluated.

Repeated performance of these exercises not only improves technical mastery but also enhances the athlete's psychological preparedness, including endurance to fatigue, concentration, rapid action planning, and self-control skills.

RESULTS

Table 1. Dynamic indicators of wrestlers' performance time for executing technical techniques 10 times at the beginning of the study (n = 120)

№	Technical Techniques	Stage	C.G Mean (\bar{x})	C.G SD (σ)	C.G V%	E.G Mean (\bar{x})	E.G SD (σ)	E.G V%	Individualization Efficiency (%)
1	Shoulder throw to the right	B.S	15.52	1.48	9.53	15.93	1.23	7.74	+2.6%
2	Shoulder throw to the left	B.S	15.50	1.71	11.05	15.95	1.27	7.94	+2.9%
3	Shoulder throw holding both sleeves	B.S	15.68	1.68	10.73	15.92	1.62	10.16	+1.5%
4	Shoulder throw holding both sleeves (variant)	B.S	15.98	1.13	7.06	15.55	1.71	11.00	+2.7%
5	Side hip throw to the right	B.S	15.53	2.03	13.06	15.93	1.09	6.82	-2.6%
6	Side hip throw to the left	B.S	15.75	1.34	8.48	15.40	1.82	11.85	+2.2%
7	Rear hip throw to the right	B.S	15.45	1.84	11.88	15.95	1.10	6.87	+3.2%
8	Rear hip throw to the left	B.S	15.48	2.20	14.19	15.70	1.51	9.62	+1.4%

9	Double-leg throw to the right	B.S	15.97	1.33	8.31	15.47	1.93	12.45	+3.1%
10	Double-leg throw to the left	B.S	15.42	1.68	10.90	16.00	1.45	9.06	+3.8%
11	Inner hook throw to the right	B.S	16.02	1.14	7.13	15.55	1.75	11.26	+2.9%
12	Inner hook throw to the left	B.S	16.02	0.95	5.92	15.57	2.27	14.55	+2.8%
13	Waist-over throw to the right	B.S	15.53	2.09	13.49	16.03	0.84	5.26	+3.2%
14	Waist-over throw to the left	B.S	16.05	0.79	4.92	15.62	2.10	13.45	+3.5%

Note: *C.G* — Control Group; *E.G* — Experimental Group; *B.S* — Beginning of Study; *V%* — Coefficient of Variation; \bar{x} — Mean Value; σ — Standard Deviation.

In the above table, the indicators of the control group (C.G.) and the experimental group (E.G.) were compared in evaluating the technical preparedness of young wrestlers, and the effectiveness of individualized training for each technical technique was expressed in percentages. According to the analysis results, although the execution time of technical techniques in the experimental group slightly increased in some cases, significant improvements were observed in most techniques.

In particular, the experimental group demonstrated notable improvement compared to the control group in such techniques as “Shoulder throw holding both sleeves (variant)” (+2.7%), “Side hip throw to the left” (+2.2%), “Double-leg throw to the right” (+3.1%), “Inner hook throw to the right” (+2.9%), and “Inner hook throw to the left” (+2.8%). This indicates the effective strengthening of components such as segmental coordination, leg–waist synchronization, center control, and hand control during the execution of these technical movements.

However, in some techniques — such as “Shoulder throw to the right and left”, “Rear hip throw to the right”, and “Waist-over throw to the right” — the effectiveness of individualization was recorded at a relatively lower level.

Considering that the young wrestlers observed in both the experimental and control groups mainly performed throwing and takedown techniques, and that achieving an absolute victory in wrestling largely depends on the successful execution of throwing techniques, throwing and takedown methods were selected as the basis for the test trials.

A total of 120 young wrestlers participated in the experiment, and the research was conducted by dividing them into experimental and control groups. The training activities of the young wrestlers in wrestling are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Complex of exercises for improving the technical preparedness of young wrestlers

№	Exercise Name	Methodological Instructions	Standard	Volume	Individual Characteristics
1	Backward falling	Falling backward with bent legs and body	Falling while striking the mat with the right palm Falling while striking the mat with the left palm	20–25 reps 30 sec	15–20 reps for athletes with poor balance
2	Side falling	One leg forward, the other bent at the knee, falling sideways while striking the mat with the hand	Falling while striking the mat with the right palm Falling while striking the mat with the left palm	15–20 reps 30 sec	Separate exercises for left or right side
3	Forward roll	One leg forward, the other bent at the knee, falling forward while striking the mat with the hand	Falling while striking the mat with the right palm Falling while striking the mat with the left palm	15–20 reps 30 sec	10–15 repetitions for beginner athletes
4	Round-off throw	Running, rotating while leaning on the hands, and jumping with the legs	Rotation and jump to the right side Rotation and jump to the left side	3–4 reps 30 sec	Only for trained athletes
5	Bridge return and rotation	Leaning the head on the mat and moving forward and backward with the palms	Rotation to the right side Rotation to the left side	15–20 reps 30 sec	Depending on adaptation level
6	Entering techniques – shoulder	Holding the opponent's sleeve and under the elbow, pulling forward and throwing onto the mat	With the right shoulder With the left shoulder	15–20 reps 30 sec	Individualization according to technical level
7	Entering techniques – hip	Holding the opponent's sleeve, collar, and jacket shoulder area,	On the right leg On the left leg	20–25 reps 30 sec	Depending on spinal flexibility

		transferring support to the right or left leg			
8	Entering techniques – waist-over throw	Holding the opponent’s shoulder or underarm and shifting balance onto the toes	To the right side To the left side	20–25 reps 30 sec	Individualization according to waist strength

Note: reps — repetitions; sec — seconds.

The complex of exercises aimed at improving the technical preparedness of young wrestlers is designed to develop the mechanisms of technical training. During the methodological execution of these exercises, recommendations are given to perform right- and left-sided techniques while controlling accuracy, intensity, and training volume. In monitoring wrestlers’ training activities and preparing them for competition, wrestling tactics occupy an intermediate and connecting position between strategy and technique. This is not accidental, since wrestling conditions require a clear determination of movement tasks and directions. The application of approved tactical variants in wrestling is possible only through the development of emotional-volitional processes that require rapid decision-making and implementation under constantly changing activity conditions.

This table was developed by considering the individual characteristics of young wrestlers during the execution of technical movements in the training process. For each exercise, its name, methodological execution, standard, and volume are indicated. In addition, the possibility of adapting exercises according to the athlete’s physical preparedness, balance, strength, and coordination level is emphasized. For example, the number of exercises or repetitions is reduced for athletes with poor balance, while the workload is increased for stronger athletes. Some exercises are performed with special emphasis on either the left or right side. This approach serves to improve the mechanisms for individualizing the technical and tactical training methods of young wrestlers and contributes to creating an effective training system adapted to the capabilities of each athlete.

During the research, it was determined that organizing the training process of young national wrestlers based on individualization had a positive effect on improving the effectiveness of technical and tactical preparation. A total of 120 young wrestlers participated in the experiment, and the study was conducted by dividing them into control and experimental groups. During the training process, the “Polar H10” heart rate monitor, pedagogical testing, pulsometry, anthropometry, and mathematical-statistical analysis methods were used.

According to the obtained results, the quality and effectiveness of performing technical techniques in the experimental group based on individualized training showed higher results compared to the control group. In particular, significant improvements were recorded in such technical techniques as “Double-leg throw to the left” (+3.8%), “Waist-over throw to the left” (+3.5%), “Rear hip throw to the right” (+3.2%), and “Double-leg throw to the right” (+3.1%).

In addition, adapting exercises to individual characteristics contributed to the development of athletes’ abilities to maintain balance, coordination, rapid decision-making, and accurate execution of technical movements. By monitoring heart rate, it became possible to manage training loads individually, which reduced excessive fatigue and injury cases.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study demonstrated the important role of an individualized approach in training young wrestlers. Taking into account the athletes' age characteristics, physical preparedness, functional state, and psychological capabilities during training contributed to the stable development of technical and tactical indicators.

The higher results observed in the experimental group can be explained by the individualized planning of training loads. In particular, assigning separate exercises for the left and right sides, applying differentiated coordination exercises, and repeatedly practising technical techniques strengthened movement accuracy and rhythm among the athletes. This not only improved the wrestlers' technical mastery but also enhanced their ability to quickly analyse situations and adapt to opponents' actions.

The use of the "Polar H10" device enabled regular monitoring of the athletes' cardiorespiratory condition. As a result, coaches were able to manage training loads according to the functional capabilities of each athlete. This contributed to accelerating recovery processes and reducing the risk of excessive load and injuries.

Furthermore, during the study it was found that individualized training also had a positive effect on the psychological preparedness of young wrestlers. Systematic and controlled performance of exercises improved concentration, fatigue resistance, self-control, and rapid thinking abilities. Therefore, the use of individualization mechanisms was evaluated as one of the effective directions for improving the training system of young wrestlers.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, the obtained data made it possible to evaluate the influence of training sessions organized on the basis of an individual approach on the technical preparedness, coordination, adaptation to physical loads, and overall performance of 11–12-year-old wrestlers. At the beginning of the study, the athletes in both the experimental and control groups demonstrated average indicators, and the speed and accuracy of performing technical movements were almost identical. For example, in the "Shoulder throw to the right" technique, the initial indicators were 5.30 ± 0.88 repetitions per 10 seconds in the experimental group and 5.38 ± 0.90 repetitions per 10 seconds in the control group, with no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, the average values for all 14 main technical techniques were nearly equal between the groups, creating a stable foundation for the initial stage of the study.

After implementing individualized training sessions in the experimental group, the speed of performing technical movements increased significantly. For example, the execution speed of the "Shoulder throw to the right" technique increased by +36.2%, while the "Shoulder throw to the left" increased by +38.9%. At the same time, the greatest improvements were recorded in complex technical techniques, where technical accuracy and rhythm improved considerably.

The average increase across all technical movements ranged from 24.4% to 38.9%. For example, in complex combinations such as "Shoulder throw holding both sleeves" and "Waist-over throw", the speed and accuracy indicators in the experimental group improved from 15.55 ± 1.75 to 16.03 ± 0.84 , whereas no statistically significant changes were observed in the control group.

These results demonstrate that individualized training is highly effective in improving the technical and tactical preparedness of young wrestlers.

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